

ON THE k -ADDITIVE UNIQUENESS OF SUMS OF CONSECUTIVE SQUARES FOR MULTIPLICATIVE FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

Let $k \geq 2$ be an integer and \mathcal{T} be the set consisting of all sums of consecutive squares. We prove that \mathcal{T} is a k -additive uniqueness set for the set of multiplicative functions. That is, if a multiplicative function f satisfies a multivariate Cauchy's functional equation $f(x_1 + x_2 + \cdots + x_k) = f(x_1) + f(x_2) + \cdots + f(x_k)$ for arbitrary $x_1, \dots, x_k \in \mathcal{T}$, then f is the identity function $f(n) = n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

1. Introduction

An arithmetic function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is called *multiplicative* if $f(1) = 1$ and $f(mn) = f(m)f(n)$ whenever $\gcd(m, n) = 1$. Let \mathcal{M} denote the set of complex valued multiplicative functions.

A set $E \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is called an *additive uniqueness set* of a set of arithmetic functions \mathcal{F} if $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is uniquely determined under the condition

$$f(m + n) = f(m) + f(n) \text{ for all } m, n \in E. \quad (1)$$

For example, \mathbb{N} and $\{1\} \cup 2\mathbb{N}$ are trivially additive uniqueness sets of \mathcal{M} .

This concept was first introduced by C. A. Spiro [9] in 1992. She proved that the set of primes is an additive uniqueness set of $\mathcal{M}_0 = \{f \in \mathcal{M} \mid f(p_0) \neq 0 \text{ for some prime } p_0\}$. Later on, Spiro's work has been extended in many directions.

Let $k \geq 2$ be a fixed integer. If there is only one function $f \in \mathcal{F}$ satisfying $f(x_1 + x_2 + \cdots + x_k) = f(x_1) + f(x_2) + \cdots + f(x_k)$ for arbitrary $x_i \in E$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, then E is called a *k -additive uniqueness set* of \mathcal{F} .

In 2010, Fang [4] proved that the set of primes is a 3-additive uniqueness set of \mathcal{M}_0 . In 2013, Dubickas and Šarka [3] generalized Fang's result to sums of arbitrary primes.

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In 1996, Chung [1] proved the following result.

Theorem 1. *Let $f \neq 0$ be a multiplicative function. If f fulfills the condition*

$$f(m^2 + n^2) = f(m^2) + f(n^2)$$

for all positive integers m and n , then

- $f(4) = 0$ or $f(4) = 4$,
- $f(q^{2k}) = (f(q^2))^k$ for all positive integers q and k ,
- if $f(4) = 4$, then $f(m^2) = m^2$ for all positive integers m .

In particular, the set \mathcal{S} of positive squares is not an additive uniqueness set for multiplicative functions.

In 1999, Chung and Phong [2] showed that the set of positive triangular numbers $T_n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and the set of positive tetrahedral numbers $Te_n = \frac{n(n+1)(n+2)}{6}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ are new additive uniqueness sets for \mathcal{M} and Park [6] extended their work to sums of k triangular numbers, $k \geq 3$.

Park [5] proved that \mathcal{S} is a k -additive uniqueness set of \mathcal{M} for every $k \geq 3$. In 2022, he [7] proved that the set

$$W = \{a^2 + b^2 : (a, b) \neq (0, 0)\} = \{1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 13, 16, 17, \dots\}$$

of numbers which are representable as sums of two squares is an additive uniqueness set for multiplicative functions.

Set $s_n = \sum_{i=0}^n i^2$ and let

$$\mathcal{T} = \{s_m - s_n \mid m > n \geq 0, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}\} = \{1, 4, 5, 9, 13, 14, 16, 25, 29, \dots\}.$$

be the set of all finite sums of consecutive squares.

Note that if $W(x)$ is the counting function for the set W , then by Landau's theorem, $W(x) \sim \frac{Bx}{\sqrt{\log x}}$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$, where B is an explicitly defined positive constant. On the other hand, for the counting function of \mathcal{T} , we have

$$x^{2/3}(\log x)^{-2-\log 2-\epsilon} \ll T(x) \ll x^{2/3},$$

(see [10]). Thus, the set \mathcal{T} is sparser than W .

Although \mathcal{T} is a 0-density subset of \mathbb{N} , it has a nice additive structure. Platiel and Rung [8] proved that \mathcal{T} forms an additive basis of the exact order 3, i.e. each nonnegative integer can be written as the sum of at most three numbers from \mathcal{T} .

The main result of this short note is the following theorem.

Theorem 2. Fix $k \geq 2$. The set \mathcal{T} consisting of all finite sums of consecutive squares is a k -additive uniqueness set of \mathcal{M} , namely, if a multiplicative function f satisfies

$$f(x_1 + x_2 + \cdots + x_k) = f(x_1) + f(x_2) + \cdots + f(x_k)$$

for arbitrary $x_1, \dots, x_k \in \mathcal{T}$, then f is the identity function.

Since $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{T}$, the k -additivity of \mathcal{T} for $k \geq 3$ immediately follows from the k -additivity of \mathcal{S} . For $k \geq 4$, we will present an alternative, much simpler proof.

2. Proof

Proof of Theorem 2. The proof consists of four cases.

Case I: $k = 2$. Trivially, $f(1) = 1$ and $f(2) = 2$. If $f(4) = 0$, then $f(5) = 1$, $f(9) = 2f(4) + 1 = 1$, and $f(14) = f(9) + f(5) = 2$. But this would lead to a contradiction:

$$\begin{aligned} f(28) &= f(7)f(4) = 0 \\ &= f(14) + f(14) = 4 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $f(4) = 4$ and $f(n) = n$ for $n \leq 10$. Next, we use induction on n . Suppose that $f(n) = n$ for $n < N$. If N is not a prime power, then $N = ab$ with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and $f(N) = N$ by the multiplicativity of f and the induction hypothesis. Thus, we may assume that N is a prime power.

Let $N = 2^r$ with $r \geq 4$. Assume that 2^r is fixed by f for all $r \leq 2m$. Then $f(2^{2m+1}) = 2^{2m+1}$ since

$$f(2^{2m+1}) = f(2^{2m} + 2^{2m}) = f(2^{2m}) + f(2^{2m}).$$

We obtain $f(2^{2(m+1)}) = 2^{2(m+1)}$ by calculating $f(5 \cdot 2^{2m})$ in two ways:

$$f(5 \cdot 2^{2m}) = f(5) \cdot f(2^{2m})$$

and

$$f(5 \cdot 2^{2m}) = f(2^{2(m+1)} + 2^{2m}) = f(2^{2(m+1)}) + f(2^{2m}).$$

Now let $N = p^r$ with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and assume that $f(n) = n$ for all $n < N$. Then there exist positive integers x and y such that

$$p^r = x^2 + y^2.$$

So, from Theorem 1, we get

$$f(p^r) = f(x^2 + y^2) = f(x^2) + f(y^2) = x^2 + y^2 = p^r.$$

Let $P_n = 1^2 + 2^2 + \dots + n^2$ be the n th square pyramidal number. Note that $P_n \in \mathcal{T}$ and $P_n = \frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6}$. By an inductive argument, we have $f(P_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n f(i^2) = P_n$.

Next, consider the case $N = p^r$ with $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ and assume that $f(n) = n$ for all $n < N$. If r is even, then $p^r = 4m + 1$ and it cannot be a sum of two positive squares. Note that

$$P_{2m} + P_{4m+1} = (2m + 1)(3m + 1)(4m + 1).$$

In this case, $\gcd(2m + 1, 4m + 1) = \gcd(3m + 1, 4m + 1) = \gcd(2m + 1, 3m + 1) = 1$ and $2m + 1, 3m + 1 < 4m + 1$. Hence, $f(4m + 1) = 4m + 1$.

If r is odd, then $N = p^r = 4m + 3$ and we have the identity

$$P_{2m+1} + P_{4m+2} = (4m + 3)(2m + 1)(3m + 2).$$

Note that, $\gcd(2m + 1, 4m + 3) = \gcd(3m + 2, 4m + 3) = \gcd(2m + 1, 3m + 2) = 1$ and $2m + 1, 3m + 2 < 4m + 3$. Thus, $f(4m + 3) = 4m + 3$.

Case II: $k = 3$. Since $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{T}$, this immediately follows from the 3-additivity of \mathcal{S} .

Case III: $k = 4$. Platiel and Rung's theorem guarantees that every positive integer can be written as a sum of three numbers from \mathcal{T} some of which possibly vanish. But, since $9 \in \mathcal{T}$ and

$$n = (n - 9) + 9 = (n - 9) + 4 + 5 = (n - 9) + 4 + 4 + 1,$$

every integer $n > 9$ can be written as a sum of four positive numbers from \mathcal{T} .

Note that $f(4) = 4$, $f(7) = f(4 + 1 + 1 + 1) = 7$ and $f(10) = f(4 + 4 + 1 + 1) = 10$. From

$$\begin{cases} f(20) = 4f(5) = f(14 + 4 + 1 + 1) = 7f(2) + 6 \\ f(2)f(5) = 10 \end{cases}$$

we obtain two solutions

$$f(2) = -\frac{20}{7}, f(5) = -\frac{7}{2} \quad \text{or} \quad f(2) = 2, f(5) = 5.$$

But the first case would lead to a contradiction:

$$\begin{aligned} f(14) &= f(5 + 4 + 4 + 1) = \frac{11}{2} \\ &= f(7 \cdot 2) = 7f(2) = -20. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can conclude that $f(2) = 2$ and $f(5) = 5$. From the equalities $f(12) = 4f(3) = f(5 + 5 + 1 + 1)$, $f(8) = f(5 + 1 + 1 + 1)$, $f(18) = 2f(9) = f(5 + 5 + 4 + 4)$, we obtain $f(3) = 3$, $f(8) = 8$, $f(9) = 9$ and f should be the identity function by induction.

Case IV: $k \geq 5$. It is clear that the sum of k numbers from \mathcal{T} can represent k , but cannot represent any number from 1 through $k - 1$. Since sums of four numbers from \mathcal{T} represent all integers greater than or equal to 10, the sum

$$\underbrace{1 + \cdots + 1}_{k-4 \text{ times}} + x + y + z + w,$$

where $x, y, z, w \in \mathcal{T}$, can represent all integers greater than or equal to $k + 6$.

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} (k - 2) + 14 &= (k - 2) \cdot 1 + 13 + 1 \\ &= (k - 2) \cdot 1 + 9 + 5, \\ (k - 3) + 15 &= (k - 3) \cdot 1 + 5 + 5 + 5 \\ &= (k - 3) \cdot 1 + 13 + 1 + 1, \\ (k - 4) + 16 &= (k - 4) \cdot 1 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 \\ &= (k - 4) \cdot 1 + 9 + 5 + 1 + 1 \\ (k - 4) + 43 &= (k - 4) \cdot 1 + 13 + 13 + 13 + 4 \\ &= (k - 4) \cdot 1 + 36 + 5 + 1 + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Let $x = f(4)$, $y = f(5)$, $z = f(9)$ and $w = f(13)$. The above equalities give rise to the system of equations

$$\begin{cases} 1 + w = y + z \\ 3y = w + 2 \\ 4x = y + z + 2 \\ 3w + x = xz + y + 2. \end{cases}$$

The solutions are

$$\begin{aligned} f(4) &= f(5) = f(9) = f(13) = 1 \\ f(4) &= 4, f(5) = 5, f(9) = 9, f(13) = 13. \end{aligned}$$

Consider the first solution set $f(4) = f(5) = f(9) = f(13) = 1$. Arrange positive numbers from \mathcal{T} into an increasing sequence and let x_n denote the n th term. Then $f(x_1) = f(x_2) = f(x_3) = f(x_4) = f(x_5) = 1$. Observe that, every x_n with $n \geq 5$ can be written as a sum of four numbers from \mathcal{T} . From the equality

$$\begin{aligned} (k - 5) + 1 + 4 + 4 + 4 + x_e \\ = (k - 5) + 13 + x_a + x_b + x_c + x_d, \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

with $a, b, c, d < e$, we infer that $f(x_n) = 1$ for all $n \geq 5$ inductively.

But for sufficiently large n , x_n can be represented as a sum of k numbers from \mathcal{T} . So $f(x_n) = k$, which is a contradiction.

Hence, we conclude that $f(4) = 4$, $f(5) = 5$, $f(9) = 9$ and $f(13) = 13$. Moreover, (2) yields $f(x_n) = x_n$ for every $n \geq 1$.

If N is a sum of k positive numbers from \mathcal{T} then $f(N) = N$. Otherwise, choose an integer $M \geq k+6$ such that $\gcd(M, N) = 1$. Then M and MN can be represented as sums of k positive numbers from \mathcal{T} . By the multiplicativity of f , we get $Mf(N) = f(M)f(N) = f(MN) = MN$. Therefore, $f(N) = N$ and this completes the proof. \square

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